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Abstract

Southeast Asian states maintain deep economic ties with both the United States and China, and the region has become a major destination for supply-chain relocation from firms in both powers. Recent U.S. reindustrialization policies—including the extension of elevated tariffs to Southeast Asian exports—pose new challenges to the region's export-led growth model and to U.S. strategic positioning in the Indo-Pacific. Drawing on hedging theory, particularly Cheng-Chwee Kuik's distinction between return-maximizing and risk-contingency behaviors, this paper examines how three manufacturing-oriented, trade-dependent economies—Vietnam, Malaysia, and Indonesia—adjusted their foreign-policy and geoeconomic orientations in response to successive waves of U.S. reindustrialization from 2017 to 2026. Using a theory-driven event-coding approach, the study analyzes 66 verified foreign-policy and geoeconomic events to trace directional tilts toward Washington, Beijing, or neutrality across three U.S. administrations. The findings show that U.S. reindustrialization has not uniformly pushed Southeast Asian states toward China. Instead, different phases of U.S. policy produced qualitatively distinct hedging responses, mediated by structural factors that vary across countries. The analysis also reveals a misalignment between U.S. tariff instruments and the goals of the Indo-Pacific Strategy: tariff shocks create openings for Chinese economic leverage in the very economies U.S. industrial policy seeks to draw closer. The durability of the Indo-Pacific Strategy will depend on whether Washington can align its economic tools with its security ambitions and provide the structural conditions that enable partners to hedge coherently under intensifying great-power competition.

Keywords: U.S. reindustrialization · Indo-Pacific · Southeast Asia · Vietnam · Malaysia · Indonesia

Introduction

The momentum behind the United States' (U.S.) reindustrialization first emerged in the aftermath of the 2008 global financial crisis and accelerated sharply in the 2020s amid pandemic-induced supply chain disruptions and intensifying geopolitical competition, particularly with the People's Republic of China (PRC). The first Trump administration (2017–2021) introduced reshoring initiatives and protectionist trade measures; the Biden administration (2021–2025) expanded these efforts through major industrial policy legislation such as the CHIPS and Science Act (2021) and the Inflation Reduction Act (2022). The second Trump administration (2025–present) has further broadened this trajectory by imposing high tariffs to penalize offshoring, lowering corporate taxes to incentivize domestic manufacturing, and reducing environmental compliance costs to stimulate domestic energy production.

This paper examines how the evolution of American industrial policy may reshape Southeast Asian states' relations with China—Washington's principal strategic competitor—and what these shifts imply for the U.S.' long-term strategic posture in the broader Indo-Pacific. The analysis extends beyond economic dynamics. Southeast Asian governments must weigh a complex interplay of economic, political, and security interests when navigating relations with major powers.

Although International Relations (IR) scholarship has long debated the boundaries between balancing, bandwagoning, and hedging (e.g., Walt 1987; Haacke 2019), this paper employs these concepts as a broad analytical framework for interpreting Southeast Asian responses to U.S. policy shifts. Hedging remains particularly salient in Southeast Asia, where most states deepen economic ties with Beijing while simultaneously sustaining security cooperation with Washington (Kuik 2008, 2016, 2021). While existing literature highlights the region's general preference for hedging, this paper asks whether the pattern has shifted in response to U.S. industrial policy changes across the first Trump term, the Biden administration, and the current second Trump administration.

Following Cheng-Chwee Kuik's (2008, 2016, 2021) influential work, hedging is not simply a midpoint between balancing and bandwagoning, nor is it directed at any single country. Rather, states hedge against risks that threaten regime survival and domestic stability (Kuik 2008, 2016, 2021; Haacke 2019). Hedging often involves pursuing contradictory or counterintuitive policies to create fallback options (Kuik 2016). Although Southeast Asian states are the most frequently cited examples, even U.S. allies and partners hedge in various ways (Kuik 2008, 2016, 2021). The motivations, degrees, and forms of hedging differ across countries, shaped by domestic political considerations, elite perceptions, and assessments of external risks. Importantly, elites do not always link their choices regarding the U.S. to their choices

regarding China across all issue areas (Kuik 2008, 2016, 2021). The extent to which each Southeast Asian country is affected by U.S. reindustrialization also influences how it recalibrates its foreign-policy responses.

Against this backdrop, the paper examines two central questions. First, how does U.S. reindustrialization—as both a trade and industrial policy—shape economic and trade developments in Southeast Asia, particularly among the member states of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN)? This requires attention to both regional patterns and country-level variation. Second, do these economic shifts influence how individual Southeast Asian states recalibrate their political, diplomatic, trade, and security relations with the U.S.? A related sub-question concerns whether, and in what ways, the China factor conditions these recalibrations. To address these questions, the paper draws on economic data, academic literature, policy analyses, and media reporting, combining macroeconomic assessment with an interpretivist analysis of foreign-policy behavior.

The sections that follow proceed in three steps. The next section evaluates the economic implications of U.S. reindustrialization for ASEAN using macroeconomic indicators. Within this analysis, Vietnam, Malaysia, and Indonesia (VIM) emerge as particularly instructive cases for deeper comparison. The third section therefore explains the comparative framework and outlines the methodology and data used to assess their foreign-policy responses across the 2017–2026 period. Section four provides an empirical comparison of VIM—three states that hedge for different reasons and in different ways while section five clarifies whether and how U.S. reindustrialization has affected their relations with both Washington and Beijing, as well as how their hedging behaviors have evolved over time. The sixth section considers the broader implications for regional hedging patterns, China’s potential leverage, and the U.S’ long-term strategic posture in the Indo-Pacific. The final section concludes with directions for future research.

US Industrialization’s Impacts on Southeast Asia: Macroeconomic Trends

Southeast Asian economies have long been embedded in the “flying geese” development model articulated by Kaname Akamatsu (1935), progressing from import dependence to domestic production and eventually export-oriented industrialization (Chow 2024). Japan and the newly industrialized economies—South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and Singapore—initially drove this pattern, relocating industries to Southeast Asia as wages rose at home. From the mid-2000s, China assumed a central role through its “going out” strategy and later the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) (Chen

2022). Today, Southeast Asia maintains deep economic ties with both the U.S. and the PRC, and firms from both countries have diversified their supply chains by relocating operations to the region in response to geopolitical and geoeconomic pressures (e.g., Gomes 2026; Ha 2026).

Recent commentaries (e.g., Gomes 2026; Ha 2026), however warn that the Trump administration's reindustrialization agenda threatens Southeast Asia's position. By imposing new tariffs and tightening scrutiny on transshipment, Washington risks undermining Southeast Asia's role as a manufacturing base for both American and Chinese firms. The 2026 Section 301 actions—targeting sixteen partner countries, including six in Southeast Asia—signal a shift away from earlier friend-shoring commitments. Analysts (e.g., Gomes 2026) argue that these measures could push Southeast Asian states closer to China at a moment when Beijing's regional influence is already expanding, thereby weakening US diplomatic leverage in the Indo-Pacific arena.

Critics further contend that US demands for bilateral concessions erode the multilateral, rules-based trading system. Southeast Asian governments are increasingly pressured to align with US economic-security regulations in exchange for continued market access (Ha 2026). Yet the resulting “deals” are executive understandings rather than formal trade agreements, lacking legislative ratification and enforceable dispute-settlement mechanisms (Ha 2026). This asymmetry enhances US trade leverage while leaving Southeast Asian states with limited recourse—deepening their structural vulnerability and weakening global trade governance.

These critiques highlight the political and normative costs of US reindustrialization, but macroeconomic data presents a more complex picture. The Oxford Economics–Hinrich Foundation report (Nguyen, Tan, and Oxford Economics 2026) shows that although Southeast Asia faces significant tariff exposure—Myanmar (40%), Vietnam (20%), and Thailand (19%)—the region has demonstrated notable resilience compared with even North America. Vietnam has absorbed the sharpest shock: greenfield foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows fell 40 percent year-on-year between April and September 2025, and semiconductor and automotive original equipment manufacturer (OEM) investments declined by more than 88 percent. Vietnam's reliance on Chinese inputs (13 percent of production, versus 5 percent in Malaysia) has made it particularly vulnerable to US transshipment scrutiny (Nguyen, Tan, and Oxford Economics 2026).

US policies have also accelerated the diversion of FDI out of China and into the broader Asian region. Because multinational enterprises (MNEs) still depend on China's scale and supplier depth, they prefer to diversify while remaining geographically proximate. Southeast Asia therefore captures a significant share of reallocated capital. The Oxford Economics–Hinrich Foundation report (Nguyen, Tan,

and Oxford Economics 2026) suggests that Vietnam, India, Malaysia, and Indonesia (VIMI) have emerged as the principal beneficiaries (Nguyen, Tan, and Oxford Economics 2026). Malaysia's experience is illustrative: its FDI inflows rose 21% in the six months following the 2025 tariff announcement, driven by a strong supplier base and a 111% surge in semiconductor investment. Region-wide, Asia's FDI inflows declined by only 12.8%, compared with a global contraction of 31.1% and a 59.3% plunge in North America (Nguyen, Tan, and Oxford Economics 2026).

This macro-level resilience does not negate the micro-level pressures facing firms. As Ha (2026) notes, many companies have renegotiated contracts at lower prices while absorbing higher compliance costs, eroding profitability. But at the regional level, Southeast Asia's structural attractiveness and its ability to capture redirected investment have mitigated the overall economic impact of US reindustrialization.

In this new normal, Southeast Asian governments continue to recalibrate their relations with Washington and Beijing across economic, political, and security domains. Existing scholarship has documented how intensifying great-power competition — including Sino-Russian alignment (Chen et al. 2025; Chen and Taylor forthcoming) — has deepened the structural pressures on ASEAN states, prompting intensified hedging strategies rather than clear alignment (Chen and Taylor forthcoming). The present study builds on this foundation by operationalizing hedging behavior at the event level across the 2017–2026 period. The next step in the analysis assesses whether these evolving structural pressures have produced observable shifts in Southeast Asian hedging behavior from the first to the second Trump terms. Before turning to that assessment, the methods and data used in this study are outlined, including the rationale for selecting specific cases for comparative analysis.

Methods and Data

This study employs a review of foreign policy and geoeconomic events combined with a comparative case study design to analyze shifting hedging behaviors among three Southeast Asian states between 2017 and 2026. This section first explains the case selection, followed by how foreign policy events were collected and coded for analysis.

Case Selection

In principle, a comprehensive analysis would compare all eleven ASEAN member states. However, because this study emphasizes deep, context-rich examination of each country's strategic behavior—necessary for accurately assessing how US reindustrialization affects foreign policy responses—a full ASEAN-wide comparison is not feasible within the scope of a single article. Qualitative case studies are therefore prioritized over broad-N comparison.

Case selection is informed by data and analysis from the Hinrich Foundation and Oxford Economics report mentioned above, which identifies the VIMI economies as the emerging anchors of the new “Factory Asia.” Among these, Vietnam, Indonesia, and Malaysia are ASEAN members and share structural similarities as manufacturing-oriented, trade-dependent economies exposed to shifts in US industrial and supply-chain policy. These three countries have also been identified as important destinations for both American and Chinese FDI amid US reindustrialization efforts. They therefore constitute a set of most-similar cases for examining whether and how US reindustrialization has altered their foreign policy behavior toward Washington, and whether changes in their US policies have produced corresponding adjustments in their China policies. The empirical analysis investigates these questions through the lens of hedging theory and event-level foreign policy tracing. The next sub-section explains how foreign policy events are collected.

Foreign Policy Events Collection and Coding

The analysis draws on established hedging frameworks in the IR literature—particularly Kuik’s (2008, 2016, 2021) framework that distinguishes return-maximizing from risk-contingency behaviors. Using this framework, this study analyzes event-level tracing of foreign policy actions across the 2017–May 2026 period. This period spans three distinct phases of US industrial policy: the first Trump administration’s tariff shocks (2017–2020), the Biden administration’s institutionalization of supply chain policy through instruments such as the CHIPS and Science Act (2021–2024), and the second Trump administration’s escalated tariffs and retreat from friendshoring commitments (2025–2026 when this paper was written). Tracing hedging behavior across these phases allows this study to assess whether and how shifts in US reindustrialization policy produce corresponding adjustments in VIM’s foreign policy.

Understanding that Southeast Asian countries’ strategic thinking towards the U.S. and China encompasses a mixture of military, economic, and political considerations (Goh 2007), the foreign policy and geoeconomic events that this study codes encompasses these dimensions. Events such as arms acquisitions, military exercises, diplomatic upgrades, decisions related to the BRI, and strategically significant geoeconomic events, including major FDI approvals and supply chain investment decisions are treated as verifiable indicators of US tilt, China tilt, or hedging behaviors. Events were included if they constituted concrete, observable state-level actions. FDIs can be primarily corporate rather than state actions, but they are included where host governments actively facilitated or approved the investment and where the investment pattern constitutes a verifiable indicator of hedging orientation, consistent with the growing IR literature on geoeconomic statecraft.

This approach is well established in qualitative IR research and Southeast Asia-focused studies, where observable acts serve as proxies for underlying strategic preferences (Goh 2007; Kuik 2008; Haacke 2019). This is not to say that observable patterns necessarily reflect well-calculated strategies. Kuik (2021) considers hedging as rather more like instinctive behaviors that occurs in uncertain situations where risks might affect countries' prioritized behaviors.

Foreign policy events were identified and coded using a structured coding manual operationalizing Kuik's (2008, 2016, 2021) hedging framework. Each event was classified along five dimensions — direction of tilt, hedging category, issue area, US-China linkage, and impact level — drawing on publicly reported, verifiable state-level actions across the 2017–May 2026 period. An initial dataset was generated using Claude Sonnet 4.6 (Anthropic), drawing on its training knowledge as a first-pass identification of relevant events. This dataset was subsequently verified and corrected against live web sources, also using Claude Sonnet 4.6 (Anthropic). Live web sources include primary government documents, official press releases, and policy outlets such as Reuters, Nikkei Asia, and The Diplomat — constituting a second, independent evidence base. Events from 2025 to May 2026 were collected exclusively through live web search, as they post-date Claude's training cutoff of August 2025. This process constitutes inter-source triangulation. The author independently verified each event against its cited sources and applied the coding manual as a second coder, adjudicating discrepancies between the Claude-generated output and the verified source material, yielding 24 events for Vietnam, 22 for Malaysia, and 20 for Indonesia. The author's manual verification proved essential: 47 errors were identified and corrected, ranging from date inaccuracies, misattributed actors to events incorrectly compressed across multiple years to coding discrepancies. While the dataset is not exhaustive, it is sufficient to identify patterns and trajectories, offering interpretive and indicative analysis rather than a fully replicable systematic coding exercise. This approach carries five limitations, which are addressed below.

First, the review draws predominantly on English-language, Western, and Singapore-based sources. Governmental websites from China, US, and Malaysia are examined too as the author can process Chinese and English materials. Sources in Bahasa Indonesia, Vietnamese, and Malay remains under-represented, which may skew interpretations of domestic elite debates, ideological drivers, and historically rooted foreign policy orientations that are more visible in non-English sources. Second, assigning a position on the hedging spectrum inevitably involves interpretive judgement. As several scholars note, hedging is analytically complex and difficult to operationalize consistently; different researchers often classify the same foreign policy acts in divergent ways (Haacke 2019; Goh 2007; Kuik 2008, 2016). Given this inherent

ambiguity, reasonable — and sometimes substantial — variation in coding is to be expected. No formal inter-coder reliability statistic was calculated; coding consistency therefore rests on the author’s judgement and the transparent documentation of coding decisions in the accompanying dataset. Third, as noted, the Claude-assisted event identification and web-source verification approach offers flexibility and breadth, but cannot guarantee exhaustive coverage. Lower-salience events, those reported primarily in non-English outlets, or those embedded in classified or non-public diplomatic exchanges may have been missed. The dataset should therefore be understood as indicative rather than comprehensive, sufficient to identify patterns and trajectories rather than to support systematic quantitative inference. Fourth, the 2025–May 2026 events are much closer to the time of writing and therefore less extensively reported and analyzed than earlier events, making those years’ coding more provisional than earlier ones. Readers should treat 2025–2026 findings as indicative of emerging trajectories rather than settled patterns, subject to revision as the historical record matures and more comprehensive reporting becomes available. Fifth, the framework applied in this study focuses on hedging between the U.S. and China, treating great-power competition as the primary axis around which smaller states position themselves. However, hedging options are not restricted to global power relations. Southeast Asian states also hedge against regional powers, sub-regional dynamics, and domestic political pressures that may be only loosely connected to U.S.–China rivalry. Vietnam’s historically complex relationship with China, Malaysia’s management of inter-ethnic domestic politics, and Indonesia’s ASEAN leadership ambitions all generate hedging imperatives that cannot be reduced to the bilateral U.S.–China axis. Also, hedging options are not restricted to global power relations. Countries can hedge by upgrading their third-party contacts, or by strengthening ASEAN. Future research should extend the hedging framework to encompass these multi-level and non-dyadic dimensions.

Different Hedging Patterns in VIM

Based on the original data, surprising patterns are observed. Overall, the VIM countries have more US tilts than China tilts, with Vietnam having the most US tilts than its China tilts, followed by Malaysia and Indonesia (Table 1).

Table 1. Event Count, Direction of Tilt, and Hedging Category— Vietnam, Malaysia and Indonesia (2017–2026)

Country	Total Recorded Events	Direction of Tilt			Hedging Category		Linked to US-China Rivalry	High Impact Events
		US Tilt	China Tilt	Neutral	Return-Maximizing	Risk-Contingency		
Vietnam	24	14 (58%)	7 (29%)	3 (13%)	14 (58%)	10 (42%)	14 (58%)	17 (71%)
Malaysia	22	10 (45%)	7 (32%)	5 (23%)	13 (59%)	9 (41%)	14 (64%)	19 (86%)
Indonesia	20	8 (40%)	6 (30%)	6 (30%)	9 (45%)	11 (55%)	4 (20%)	16 (80%)
Total	66	32 (48%)	20 (30%)	14 (21%)	36 (55%)	30 (45%)	32 (48%)	52 (79%)

Note. Dataset: 66 events (Vietnam = 24, Malaysia = 22, Indonesia = 20), 2017–2026, verified by author.

Direction of Tilt: US = event primarily signals alignment with or delivers returns from the US relationship; China = China relationship; Neutral = ASEAN-centric, multilateral, or ambiguous.

Hedging Category: Return-Maximizing = pursuing economic/diplomatic gains; Risk-Contingency = maintaining fallback/insurance (Kuik 2008, 2016, 2021).

Linked to US-China Rivalry: events that explicitly respond to or connect with US-China rivalry dynamics.

High Impact: events coded as structurally significant, changing bilateral relationships or committing major resources.

Figure 1 further shows that Vietnam exhibited near-zero China-tilt from 2018 to 2022, then a dual surge in both US and China-tilt from 2023 onward. Vietnam shows a clear US-tilt acceleration from 2021 through 2024, culminating in the Comprehensive Strategic Partnership (CSS) upgrade in 2023 and deepening technology and semiconductor integration with the US. However, this trajectory does not represent a straightforward drift — China-tilt events resurge strongly from 2023 onward, and by 2025–2026 Vietnam is simultaneously deepening ties with both powers. The post-2023 pattern is better characterized as *dual intensification* than US drift: Vietnam upgraded its relationship with the US to its highest diplomatic tier while simultaneously deepening institutional ties with China. Key examples include Xi Jinping’s December 2023 visit to Hanoi, the 2025 Huawei and ZTE contracts, Hanoi’s approval of Chinese

loans for the US\$8.3 billion Lao Cai–Hanoi–Hai Phong standard-gauge railway in 2025, and President To Lam’s April 2026 visit to Beijing. The 2025 Liberation Day tariff shock appears to have accelerated this China engagement, prompting Vietnam to make substantive technology and infrastructure commitments to Beijing in direct response to U.S. trade pressure. Hanoi’s approval of Chinese financing for the railway is especially significant: it represents a reversal of its long-standing security-based resistance to Chinese infrastructure lending and is therefore coded as a high-impact event (Duan 2026).

Figure 1. Direction of tilt by year — Vietnam, Malaysia and Indonesia (2017–2026)

Note. Event counts per year by direction of tilt. US tilt (solid dark bars) = events primarily signaling alignment with or delivering returns from the US relationship; China tilt (medium grey, diagonal hatch) = China relationship; Neutral (light grey, dot hatch) = ASEAN-centric, multilateral, or ambiguous. Stars (★) denote years in which at least one event in that tilt category was coded High Impact — structurally significant acts that change bilateral relationships or commit major resources. Dataset: 66 events (Vietnam = 24, Malaysia = 22, Indonesia = 20), 2017–2026, verified by author.

Different from Vietnam, Malaysia’s hedging pattern is better characterized as episodic dual-engagement rather than consistent dual-tracking (Figure 1). US and China-tilt events occur simultaneously only in 2017, 2023, and 2025; the remaining years show either single-tilt dominance or low engagement with both powers. The relative quiet between 2019 and 2022 reflects domestic political instability rather than strategic intent—namely, three prime ministers in three years: Mahathir Mohamad, Muhyiddin Yassin, and Ismail Sabri Yaakob. The 2025 spike is the most dramatic in the dataset, with four US-tilt events and three China-tilt events in a single year after a prolonged period of muted activity.

In other words, the analytically significant pattern is the compression of dual-track hedging into peak years. Both 2023 and especially 2025 show Malaysia simultaneously securing US semiconductor FDI, signing a U.S. defense memorandum of understanding (MOU), and hosting Xi Jinping—all within the same twelve-month window. The clearest expression of Malaysia’s deliberate return-maximizing hedging emerges under Prime Minister Anwar Ibrahim (2023–2026), when the country attracted the largest U.S. tech FDI in Southeast Asia while deepening BRI cooperation, Huawei partnerships, and high-level diplomatic engagement with China.

Indonesia’s pattern is more intricate than a simple “neutral” profile. As shown in Figure 1, neutral events appear in seven of the ten years, but both US-tilted and China-tilted events also recur throughout the period. Indonesia never experiences a year of pure neutrality: in every year except 2020 and 2021, at least one directional event accompanies the neutral ones. The result is a layered pattern of simultaneous neutrality and selective alignment rather than a stable non-aligned stance.

Indonesia’s US tilt follows a distinctive arc. The 2017 entry (US = 2), driven by the Garuda Shield military exercise and the completion of the F-16 fighter aircraft programme, is the dataset’s first clear signal of a US-tilted year. This tilt then largely disappears from 2018 to 2021, when neutral events dominate and occasional China-tilted events emerge. A meaningful US tilt only reappears in 2022 with Super Garuda Shield, an expanded version of the previous Garuda Shield exercise, strengthens again in 2023, and peaks in 2025. This trajectory — early engagement with Washington, a mid-period dominated by neutrality, and a late-period deepening of security

cooperation — aligns closely with President Joko Widodo's (Jokowi's) infrastructure-first governing priorities (2017–2024) giving way to President Prabowo Subianto's more assertive security posture.

China-tilted events remain consistently low in magnitude but strikingly persistent. China appears in 2017, 2018, 2019, 2024, and 2025 — never dominant in any single year yet never absent for more than two consecutive years. This contrasts with Vietnam, where China-tilted events disappear for extended periods, and with Malaysia, where they cluster in specific phases. Indonesia's engagement with China is steady and understated — participation in the BRI, financing for the Jakarta–Bandung High-Speed Rail (HSR), and investment from Contemporary Amperex Technology Limited (CATL) — rather than episodic or dramatic.

The transition from Jokowi to Prabowo is clearly reflected in the dataset. The 2020–2021 period registers the only fully neutral years for Indonesia (US = 0, China = 0, Neutral = 1 in both years), marking the most non-aligned phase in the entire series. This corresponds to Jokowi's focus on preparing for Indonesia's G20 presidency and the constraints of COVID-19–era diplomacy. From 2022 onward, however, both US-tilted and China-tilted events reappear in parallel — Super Garuda Shield on the US side, and electric-vehicle (EV) battery and related supply-chain investments on the China side. By 2025, under Prabowo, Indonesia records its highest combined tilt score (US = 3, China = 2, Neutral = 1), with six coded events in a single year — matching Malaysia's intensity in 2025 and marking Indonesia's most active and multidirectional engagement in the dataset.

Indonesia's 2024 China-tilted entry is qualitatively distinct from all earlier episodes. The November 2024 joint statement's implicit acknowledgement of overlapping South China Sea (SCS) claims — combined with Prabowo's choice of Beijing as his first inaugural foreign visit — marks a clear departure from Jokowi's consistent stance on Indonesia's sovereignty rights in the Natuna Sea. Under Jokowi, the government repeatedly stressed that the natural resources in the North Natuna Sea were non-negotiable and that Indonesia would not enter maritime boundary talks with China, as no overlapping territorial disputes exist under international law (Connelly 2016). Unlike previous forms of return-maximizing cooperation with China, such as BRI infrastructure or high-speed rail financing, the 2024 episode touches directly on sovereignty — an area Jokowi never allowed to become negotiable. For this reason, the 2024 China-tilted entry carries disproportionate analytical weight relative to its numerical value of one.

Taken together, Indonesia's hedging behavior is best characterized as persistent, low-intensity balancing punctuated by reactive surges. Throughout the Jokowi era, China-tilted events remain steady but never dominant, while security cooperation with

Washington deepens incrementally through successive expansions of Super Garuda Shield without provoking overt Chinese pushback. The transition to Prabowo introduces qualitatively new elements — accession to the BRICS grouping, the establishment of a “2+2” security dialogue with China, and the implicit shift on SCS sovereignty language — that constitute genuine departures from Jokowi’s more institutionalized and carefully managed hedging strategy. After reviewing the foreign policy behaviors of VIM, the next section explores whether any of these are influenced by the U.S. reindustrialization policy.

Are These Hedging Patterns Driven by Trump’s Policies?

Each VIM’s hedging pattern reveals a distinct imprint of Trump-era policy shocks. With this context in place, the following sections examine how these dynamics unfolded in Vietnam, Malaysia, and Indonesia.

Vietnam

Beginning with Vietnam, Trump’s first term generated a modest but genuine US-tilt signal — but its drivers were economic, not strategic. The 2018 and 2019 US-tilt entries reflect customs tightening to avoid transshipment accusations and Vietnam’s effort to position itself as the primary destination for China-diverted FDI. These are supply-chain hedging behaviors, not diplomatic or security realignments. Vietnam was not recalibrating its strategic posture in response to Trump; it was opportunistically capturing the windfall created by US tariffs on China. This is classic return-maximizing behavior triggered by a tariff shock, not risk-contingency hedging.

The Biden period (2021–2024) produces Vietnam’s clearest and most sustained US-tilt arc. The sequence — US=2 in 2021, zero events in 2022, then US=1 in 2023 and US=3 in 2024 — reflects a shift from opportunistic gains to structural alignment. The 2023 CSP upgrade and the 2024 Samsung/NVIDIA investments embed Vietnam into US-aligned technology supply chains through physical infrastructure and long-term industrial commitments that are costly to reverse. China-tilt events reappear in 2023 (Xi’s Hanoi visit), but only at parity with US-tilt signals, not dominance. Under Biden, Vietnam’s hedging becomes institutionalized: the CSP, semiconductor partnerships, and the Amkor factory opening create durable structural ties that extend beyond any single administration.

Trump’s second term produces the most analytically complex pattern in the Vietnam dataset. In 2025, US=3 and China=3 — the only year of perfect symmetry. This is not random. It reflects Vietnam absorbing a 46% tariff shock and responding with a dual strategy: seeking a tariff accommodation with Washington while simultaneously

deepening structural ties with Beijing. The Huawei/ZTE 5G contracts and the railway financing approval are substantive commitments, not symbolic gestures. They represent genuine China-leaning moves that exceed reassurance signaling and cross into areas previously insulated from Chinese influence.

The pattern sharpens further in 2026, the only year in the dataset where Vietnam's China-tilt exceeds its US-tilt (US=1, China=2). This marks a striking reversal from the 2021–2024 trajectory. The drivers — To Lam's April 2026 Beijing visit with 32 agreements, the 3+3 security dialogue, and the railway financing— are not ceremonial. They represent institutional deepening with China across security, infrastructure, and technology simultaneously. The July 2025 tariff deal (20%) eased immediate US trade pressure, which paradoxically reduced Vietnam's incentive to maintain a strong US-alignment signal even as China engagement continued to intensify.

From comparative perspective, Vietnam is the only country among the VIM cases where the Trump effect produces a measurable sovereignty-adjacent trade-off. The Huawei/ZTE decision and the railway-financing reversal both touch domains where Vietnam had previously held firm on security grounds. In contrast, Indonesia under Jokowi never compromised Natuna sovereignty under economic pressure and consistently rejected any notion of overlapping claims. Prabowo's late-2024 shift — the joint statement's implicit acknowledgement of overlapping South China Sea claims — marks a departure from that long-standing legal-doctrinal line, but it does not yet constitute a sovereignty trade-off comparable to Vietnam's 2025–2026 concessions. Vietnam, under the Liberation Day tariff shock, crossed lines it had not crossed before. This makes Vietnam's Trump-2 response qualitatively different from the supply-chain opportunism that characterized its behavior under Trump-1.

In short, the two Trump administrations produced fundamentally different effects on Vietnam. Trump-1 created an opportunity while Trump-2 created a vulnerability: the 46% tariff hit Vietnam directly, threatening its largest export market. Vietnam's response was defensive rather than opportunistic, and this defensive posture pushed it toward China in ways that Trump-1 never did. The concessions Vietnam made to Beijing in 2025–2026 are structurally more significant than any China-tilt event in the Trump-1 period.

Vietnam's data reveals what may be the most consequential finding in this paper. The country that tilted most decisively toward the US during the Biden era also exhibits the sharpest China-tilt reversal when US tariff pressure becomes direct and severe. This exposes a paradox at the heart of US reindustrialization policy: it is possible that the states most successfully integrated into US supply chains are also the most vulnerable to US tariff shocks, and that vulnerability creates openings for China to deepen its influence precisely where US policy had invested most heavily in alignment. We only

have Vietnam as an example here. Future research can investigate other countries to verify this observation.

Malaysia

Moving from Vietnam to Malaysia, we see a markedly different pattern of responses. The first Trump administration produced almost no measurable hedging behavior in Malaysia. The 2018 tariffs triggered nothing in the Malaysia dataset — that year records zero US-tilt or China-tilt events, and only a single Neutral entry: Mahathir’s suspension of BRI projects, which was driven by domestic fiscal concerns rather than US tariff pressure (Chen 2020). This absence is analytically significant. Malaysia did not respond to Trump’s trade war the way Vietnam did because the country was absorbed in the post-Najib political transition — the unprecedented 2018 electoral turnover, the formation of the Pakatan Harapan government, and the early stages of the Najib-related investigations (Case 2017). The new administration was focused on domestic political consolidation and institutional repair, leaving little bandwidth for strategic recalibration.

The Biden period (2021–2024) brings the semiconductor FDI surge — Intel’s expansion in 2021 and the Penang boom in 2023 — yet even these developments generate only modest tilt counts. By contrast, the second Trump term produces the most concentrated burst of dual engagement in Malaysia’s entire dataset. Within a single year, Malaysia negotiated its tariff rate down from 24% to 19%, signed a US–Malaysia Agreement on Reciprocal Trade, concluded a defence MOU with Washington, and hosted Trump at the ASEAN Summit — while simultaneously receiving Xi Jinping, deepening the China-linked 5G track, and having Anwar attend the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) summit alongside Putin. The result is US=4 and China=3 in one year.

Malaysia’s pattern shows that the Trump effect is not simply a tariff shock that pushes countries toward China; it is a leverage-activation moment. As Kuik’s 2026 study argues, Malaysia’s decade-long posture of calibrated neutrality continues to function, with hedging strategies deliberately maintained to preserve room for maneuver. This aligns closely with this paper’s findings: Trump’s tariff pressure, paradoxically, gave Malaysia more diplomatic leverage than it had during the relatively stable Biden period. Malaysia used its ASEAN Chair position and its semiconductor export importance (roughly 20% of US chip imports) to extract concessions from Washington while signaling to Beijing that it remained an open and reliable partner. The threat of tariffs was the catalyst that brought both major powers to Malaysia simultaneously. This dynamic differs from Vietnam’s Trump effect — where tariff pressure pushed Hanoi toward substantive China-leaning commitments such as Huawei/ZTE and railway financing — and from Indonesia’s Trump effect, which

produced major concessions to Washington while deepening China ties in parallel. Malaysia uniquely monetized Trump-era pressure rather than being destabilized by it.

Indonesia

Turning to Indonesia, we see a pattern distinct from both Malaysia and Vietnam. The first Trump administration had almost no measurable impact on Indonesia's hedging behavior. The 2017 US-tilt events — completion of the F-16C/D upgrade program and the Garuda Shield exercise — predate the tariff war and reflect Obama-era security cooperation momentum rather than a response to Trump.

The Section 301 tariffs of 2018–2019 produced a China-tilt, not a US-tilt. While Vietnam tightened customs and captured diverted FDI, Indonesia signed the Regional Comprehensive Economic Corridor (RCEC) MOU with China's National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC) in 2018 and returned to the Belt and Road Forum (BRF) in 2019 with 23 new MOUs. These moves reflected Jakarta's infrastructure-financing priorities, not a reaction to US–China rivalry. Hence, Trump's first-term tariffs did not meaningfully shift Indonesia's tilt patterns.

The Natuna confrontations of 2019–2020 produced Neutral rather than US-tilt responses. When China's coast guard entered Indonesia's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) in December 2019 and Jokowi deployed warships in January 2020, Indonesia did not seek US support or frame the incident in US–China terms. It asserted its sovereign rights under the UNCLOS independently. This contrasts with Vietnam's 2019 Vanguard Bank standoff, where Hanoi accepted US diplomatic backing and the event was coded US-tilt.

Why did Trump's first term barely register in Indonesia's hedging? First, Indonesia's trade exposure to the US was far lower than Vietnam's or Malaysia's; China and ASEAN absorbed most of Indonesia's commodity exports. The tariff shock on China therefore created little opportunity for Indonesia, whose economy could not absorb relocated manufacturing the way Vietnam's could. Jokowi's domestic agenda was infrastructure-first, and China — not the US — offered large-scale BRI financing. Indonesia was rationally indifferent to the US–China trade war from a supply-chain perspective.

Second, domestic politics reinforced this. Indonesia's 2019 presidential election centered on infrastructure delivery — the high-speed rail, BRI projects, and the new capital Nusantara — giving China-linked economic engagement strong political logic unrelated to US–China rivalry.

Indonesia's non-response to Trump's first term is itself a finding. It challenges any claim that the 2018–2019 tariff war produced a uniform regional shift toward the US. For Indonesia, Trump 1 was largely irrelevant: it continued its BRI trajectory, handled

Natuna autonomously, and showed no measurable US-tilt.

This makes Indonesia's Trump 2 response — US=3, China=2, Neutral=1 in 2025 — all the more striking. When tariffs hit Indonesia directly at 32%, hedging intensified dramatically. The lesson is that Indonesia's hedging is tariff-activation dependent: indirect shocks to China do not move Indonesia, but direct shocks to Indonesian exports do.

Indonesia's 2025 pattern resembles Malaysia's dual surge, but the mechanism differs. Malaysia activated leverage; Indonesia made concessions. Indonesia's July 2025 trade deal required eliminating tariffs on more than 99% of US goods and committing USD 33 billion in US purchases — the largest concession package in Southeast Asia. Simultaneously, CATL broke ground on a USD 6 billion project in June 2025, and Indonesia joined BRICS in January 2025. The dual surge reflects parallel concession-making, not leverage extraction. Indonesia's Trump effect reveals the limits of hedging without structural leverage: a country that must satisfy both powers simultaneously rather than profit from their competition. The next section will show a comparative synthesis of what we have discussed so far.

Discussion and Implications for the U.S. Indo-Pacific Strategies

The empirical findings suggest that U.S. reindustrialization has produced ripple effects that extend well beyond trade and investment flows, influencing how key Southeast Asian states position themselves between Washington and Beijing. These differentiated responses carry direct consequences for the credibility and sustainability of the U.S. Indo-Pacific Strategy. This section begins with a comparative synthesis of the three cases to help clarify where U.S. policy tools reinforce its strategic objectives—and where they inadvertently undermine them.

Comparative Synthesis

Across the VIM cases, the two Trump administrations produced three distinct hedging logics, shaped not by regime type or ideology but by economic structure, domestic political priorities, and structural leverage.

Vietnam shows the clearest case of tariff-induced vulnerability. Trump's first-term tariffs on China created a supply-chain windfall that Vietnam captured through return-maximizing behavior. But when Trump's second-term tariffs hit Vietnam directly, the logic flipped: Hanoi adopted Chinese 5G infrastructure, accepted Chinese railway financing, and entered a 3+3 security dialogue — sovereignty-adjacent concessions it had previously resisted. Vietnam's hedging intensifies when tariff pressure is direct, not indirect.

Malaysia represents the opposite dynamic. Rather than being destabilized by tariff

pressure, Malaysia activated leverage. Its semiconductor centrality and ASEAN Chair position allowed it to extract concessions from Washington while simultaneously deepening ties with Beijing. The dual surge of 2025 (US=4, China=3) reflects strategic monetization of great-power competition, not vulnerability. Malaysia's Trump effect is best understood as leverage maximization, not concession-making.

Indonesia occupies a third category: tariff-activation dependence without structural leverage. Trump's first-term tariffs on China produced almost no response — Indonesia's economic structure, commodity export profile, and infrastructure-first domestic agenda made China engagement the rational default. Only when Trump's second-term tariffs hit Indonesia directly at 32% did hedging intensify. But unlike Malaysia, Indonesia lacked the structural leverage to extract returns; instead, it made parallel concessions — a sweeping US trade deal on one side, BRICS entry and CATL investment on the other. Indonesia hedges most actively when directly pressured. Its responses take the form of dual concession-making, not leverage extraction.

It is also worth noting that Indonesia's pattern supports a “structural capacity” argument that reinforces what Malaysia's data suggested. Indonesia has significant natural resources (nickel) and demographic weight, but in 2025 its hedging was more reactive than strategic. The Prabowo era introduces a new variable — personal diplomacy and “thousand friends” ideology — that makes Indonesia's hedging less institutionally predictable than Jokowi's more structured approach (Cabinet Secretariat of the Republic of Indonesia 2026). Lowy Institute's “visibility without vision in Indonesian foreign policy” assessment fits the data: high activity in 2025 but no consistent directional logic (Utama 2025), unlike Malaysia's semiconductor leverage play or Vietnam's dual intensification pattern.

Taken together, the VIM cases show that the “Trump effect” is not a uniform regional phenomenon. It is conditional. Vietnam hedges when vulnerable, Malaysia hedges when empowered, Indonesia hedges when directly targeted but without leverage to shape outcomes. The same external shock — Trump-era tariff pressure — thus produces three different hedging equilibria, revealing that Southeast Asian alignment behavior is driven less by geopolitical preference than by structural position within the global economy and the distribution of bargaining power vis-à-vis the US and China.

Implications for the US Indo-Pacific Strategy

A key implication of the above analysis is that security deepening and economic alignment do not necessarily reinforce each other. Security cooperation — such as Indonesia's Super Garuda Shield expansions or Malaysia's defence MOU with Washington — can continue even as states intensify economic engagement with China. Under tariff pressure, economic hedging becomes more China-leaning even as security

ties with Washington deepen. This decoupling challenges a core assumption of the U.S. Indo-Pacific Strategy: that economic and security partnerships move in tandem. In practice, tariff shocks weaken U.S. economic influence precisely where China is best positioned to step in.

The U.S. Indo-Pacific strategy would therefore benefit from a more differentiated partner architecture that reflects the structural asymmetries among Southeast Asian states. Malaysia's semiconductor leverage, Vietnam's deep supply-chain integration, and Indonesia's scale but limited bargaining power require distinct policy instruments rather than uniform tariff rates or identical commitments under the Indo-Pacific Economic Framework (IPEF). The IPEF, designed to provide economic architecture without market access, proved unable to shield partners from tariff exposure, leaving them structurally vulnerable to U.S. policy volatility.

A tiered partnership framework — analogous to the European Union's differentiated neighborhood policy — could offer deeper economic commitments, stronger tariff protections, and more institutionalized security cooperation to states that have made the largest structural commitments to U.S.-aligned supply chains. Such an approach would reward Malaysia's semiconductor investments and Vietnam's CSP upgrade with durable economic security, reducing the conditions under which tariff shocks push aligned partners toward China.

Finally, the study shows that China consistently exploits the windows created by U.S. policy disruptions. Xi Jinping's visits to Hanoi and Kuala Lumpur during tariff negotiations, and CATL's investment in Indonesia, illustrate a systematic strategy of offering economic anchoring precisely when U.S. policy generates uncertainty. For Washington, this underscores the need for a more proactive counter-offer architecture — one that includes credible infrastructure financing, technology transfer for next-generation industries, and multilateral economic platforms with binding commitments. Without such instruments, Southeast Asian states will continue to hedge by maintaining China as an economic anchor even as they deepen security cooperation with the U.S.

In sum, the VIM cases reveal that hedging in Southeast Asia is shaped less by geopolitical preference than by structural vulnerability, economic leverage, and the institutional depth of partnerships. In Korolev's (2025) book on "When Hedging Fails", he rightly noted that hedging becomes fragile when protective options shrink. U.S. tariff

shocks narrow Southeast Asian states' economic fallback options, increasing the risk that hedging becomes reactive rather than strategic. The durability of the Indo-Pacific Strategy will depend on whether Washington can align its economic instruments with its security ambitions — and provide the structural conditions that allow its partners to hedge coherently rather than reactively in an era of intensifying great-power competition.

Concluding Remarks

This study has examined how successive waves of U.S. reindustrialization—from the first Trump administration through Biden and into the second Trump term—have reshaped the strategic behavior of three key Southeast Asian economies. By tracing 66 foreign-policy and geoeconomic events across Vietnam, Malaysia, and Indonesia, the analysis demonstrates that hedging in Southeast Asia is neither uniform nor static. Instead, it evolves in response to shifting U.S. policy signals, domestic structural constraints, and the widening geoeconomic space created by intensifying U.S.–China rivalry.

Three findings stand out. First, U.S. tariff instruments have not produced the alignment effects Washington anticipated. Security cooperation with Washington has continued to deepen, yet economic hedging has tilted more strongly toward China under tariff pressure. This decoupling of security and economic alignment challenges a core assumption of the Indo-Pacific Strategy: that progress in one domain naturally reinforces the other. In practice, tariff shocks weaken U.S. economic influence precisely where China is best positioned to intervene.

Second, the VIM cases reveal that hedging behavior is shaped less by geopolitical preference than by structural vulnerability and economic leverage. Vietnam's supply-chain depth, Malaysia's semiconductor ecosystem, and Indonesia's scale but limited bargaining power generate distinct exposure profiles that cannot be addressed through uniform U.S. policy tools. The differentiated responses observed across the three cases underscore the need for a more tailored U.S. partner architecture—one that offers credible economic security to states making substantial commitments to U.S.-aligned supply chains.

Third, China has consistently exploited the openings created by U.S. policy volatility. High-level diplomatic engagements, targeted infrastructure financing, and strategic investments—such as Xi Jinping's visits to Hanoi and Kuala Lumpur and CATL's expansion in Indonesia—demonstrate a deliberate Chinese strategy of offering economic anchoring at precisely the moments when U.S. policy generates uncertainty. These interventions reinforce China's role as an indispensable economic partner even

for states that are simultaneously deepening security cooperation with Washington.

Taken together, these findings suggest that the durability of the U.S. Indo-Pacific Strategy will depend on whether Washington can align its economic instruments with its security ambitions. A more credible economic architecture—one that includes tariff stability, market access, infrastructure financing, and technology partnerships—would reduce the structural conditions that push Southeast Asian states toward reactive hedging. Without such alignment, the region will continue to hedge asymmetrically: relying on the U.S. for security while maintaining China as an economic anchor.

Future research should extend this event-level approach to additional ASEAN members and explore whether similar dynamics emerge in South Asia and the Pacific Islands as U.S. industrial policy continues to evolve. As great-power competition deepens, understanding how states hedge under structural uncertainty will remain central to assessing the trajectory of the Indo-Pacific order.

References

1. Akamatsu, K. (1935). Waga kuni yomo kogyohin no susei [Trend of Japanese trade in woolen goods]. *Shogyo Keizai Ronso [Journal of Nagoya Higher Commercial School]*, 13, 129-212.
2. Akamatsu, K. (1937). Waga kuni keizai hatten no sogo bensho. *Shogyo Keizai Ronso*, 15, 179-210.
3. Cabinet Secretariat of the Republic of Indonesia. (2026). President Prabowo: Indonesia must be vigilant in facing global turmoil, firmly uphold free, active politics. 2 February, <https://setkab.go.id/en/president-prabowo-indonesia-must-be-vigilant-in-facing-global-turmoil-firmly-uphold-free-active-politics/>. Accessed 27 May 2026.
4. Chow, P. C.Y. (2024). The shifting paradigm of global trade in technology. In Peter C. Y. Chow (ed.) *Technology Rivalry Between the USA and China*, p. 3-23. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
5. Beltran, S. (2026). US trade probes risk alienating ASEAN, casting doubt on future of deals. *South Morning China Post*, 18 March, <https://www.scmp.com/week-asia/economics/article/3347044/us-trade-probes-risk-alienating-asean-casting-doubt-future-deals>. Accessed 25 March 2026.
6. Case, W. (2017). Stress testing leadership in Malaysia: the 1MDB scandal and Najib Tun Razak. *The Pacific Review* 30(5): 633–654.
7. Chen, J. Y-W.; Taylor, M. (2026). The Sino-Russian relationship and its implications across the Eurasian and Indo-Pacific strategic theaters. *Communist and Post-Communist Studies* (forthcoming)
8. Chen, J. Y-W.; Taylor, M.; Gerstl, A.; Kironka, K. (2026). The challenges of Sino-Russian alignment to the liberal international order in Southeast Asia. *Asia Europe Journal* 24:125-139.
9. Chen, J. Y-W (2022). Reconciling different approaches to conceptualizing the globalization of the Belt and Road Initiative projects, *Globalizations* 19(7):1165-

10. Chen, J. Y-W (2020). Appropriate approaches to studying the BRI's actual impacts and limits, in Alfred Gerstl and Ute Wallenböck (eds.) *China's Belt and Road Initiative: Strategic and Economic Impacts on Central Asia, Southeast Asia and Central Eastern Europe*, p. 43-60. Abingdon: Routledge.
11. Duan, H. (2026). Vietnam and China lay the tracks for deeper trade connectivity. *East Asia Forum*, 28 March, <https://eastasiaforum.org/2026/03/28/vietnam-and-china-lay-the-tracks-for-deeper-trade-connectivity/>. Accessed 26 May 2026.
12. Evelyn, G. (2007). Great powers and hierarchical orders in Southeast Asia. *International Security*, 32(3), 113-157.
13. Gomes, A. (2026). Washington's new tariff wall and the transformation of US-ASEAN economic relations. *Modern Diplomacy*, 23 March, <https://moderndiplomacy.eu/2026/03/23/washingtons-new-tariff-wall-and-the-transformation-of-us-asean-economic-relations/>. Accessed 25 March 2026.
14. Ha, H. T. (2026). Southeast Asia navigates Trumpian storms: disruptions, recalibrations and adaptations. *ISEAS Perspective*, 6, 1-13.
15. Haacke, J. (2019). The concept of hedging and its application to Southeast Asia's post-Cold War security policies. *International Relations of the Asia-Pacific*, 19(3). 375-417.
16. Korolev, A. (2025). *When Hedging Fails: Structural Uncertainty, Protective Options, and Geopolitical (Im)prudence in Smaller Powers' Behaviour*. Cambridge University Press.
17. Kuik, C-C. (2008). The essence of hedging: Malaysia and Singapore's Response to a Rising China. *Contemporary Southeast Asia*, 30(2), 159-185.
18. Kuik, C-C. (2016). Malaysia between the United States and China: What do Weaker States Hedge Against? *Asian Politics & Policy*, 8(1), 155-177.
19. Kuik, C-C. (2021). Getting hedging right: A small-state perspective. *China International Strategy Review*, 3, 300-315.
20. Kuik, C-C. (2026). Assessing hedging in Trump 2.0: The case of Malaysian Neutrality, *Trends in Southeast Asia*, 5. Singapore: The ISEAS-Yusof Ishak Institute.
21. Nguyen, Q. T.; Tan, T.T.; Oxford Economics. (2026). The Trump effect: how the Us and China are driving Factor Asia's FDI evolution. Hinrich Foundation White Paper. 13 January. <https://www.hinrichfoundation.com/research/wp/fdi/us-and-china-are-driving-factory-asia-fdi-evolution>. Accessed 30 March 2026.
22. Savic, B. (2025). Southeast Asia's economic model at risk due to U.S. tariffs. *Geopolitical Intelligence Services*. <https://www.gisreportsonline.com/r/asean-tariffs/>. Accessed 25 March 2026.
23. Utama, V. R. (2025). Prabowo's first year: Visibility without vision in Indonesian foreign policy. *The Interpreter*, Lowy Institute, 23 October <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpreter/prabowo-s-first-year-visibility-without-vision-indonesian-foreign-policy>. Accessed 25 May 2026.
24. Walt, S.M. (1987). *The Origin of Alliances*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.